

Feed consumption for goat Alpine and Toggenburg breeds during the feeding period

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Abstract:

The article presents the results of studies of experiments on goats of different breeds in the conditions of Uzbekistan, studied the consumption of feed in different periods of feeding (in dairy, up to 90,120, during the preparation of fattening and 60 days of feeding).

With the development of market relations in Uzbekistan, goat breeding began to develop rapidly. Various breeds of goats began to be imported into the country. Among them, of particular interest is the highly productive goats of the Alpine and Toggenburg breeds, widely used in many countries of the world.

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During the period of experiments, identical conditions for keeping and feeding were created to ensure the same growth and development of the kids of these breeds.

In the experiments in the first month, every day the kids with the help of milk nipples were given 1.7 kg on average per head of freshly milked goat milk. Beginning at 15 days of age, within 5 days, the kids began to accustom them to compound feed and hay. Starting from 20 days of age, the volume of compound feed and hay was increased to 0.1 kg each per 1 head per day. Starting from the second month of the experiments, the volume of whole milk was reduced to 0.8 kg and 1.8 kg of milk replacer was replaced. Starting from this age, the volume of compound feed was increased to 0.2 kg, hay 0.15 kg, and 0.2 kg of hydroponic feed per head was additionally included in the goat's diet.

In the course of the experiments, a weight cycle of technology for the production of goat meat was carried out. In this technology, male goats are obtained as an offspring on the farm itself from females brought into the republic and raised to 12-14.5 months of age, reaching 55-60 kg of live weight. In this technology, efficient use of feed was achieved and high-quality goat meat was obtained.

This technology of growing goats is recommended for implementation in dairy and meat goat breeding farms in Uzbekistan.

In experiments, goats of both breeds were kept under the same conditions and diet. The technology of raising goats included the following stages - rearing, growth and preparation for fattening, as well as fattening. In different periods of the experiment, the kids showed different average daily weight gain and it was in the first 90 days - 180-200 g, 91-120 days - 110-120 g, 121-210 days - 150-165 g, with 60 days of preliminary preparation for fattening - 140-155 gr, 75 days fattening 190-200 grams per day. (Table 1.)

1- Table

In experiments with this technology, special attention was paid to the feeding of the kids and the nutritional value of the rations at all stages. In the experiments in both groups for 90 days of the dairy period, only 81 kg of goat's milk was consumed, 117 kg of milk replacer, 14.5 kg of hydroponic feed, 11.0 kg of hay, 14 kg of alfalfa haylage, 5.7 kg of wheat bran, 11 kg of special compound feed BDK for 1 head. The average nutritional value of the diet in this period was 68.3 ECO or 59.14 kg of feed units. For 1 kg of weight gain of Al goats, 3.7 c.u., 3.3 kg of dry matter, 330 MJ of metabolizable energy, and 567 g of digestible protein were used, while 153 g of digestible protein came to one feed unit. And the goats of the Toggenburg breed used 3.9 c.u., 3.47 kg of dry matter 347 MJ of metabolizable energy and 596 g of digestible protein, with 153 g of digestible protein per feed unit.

When reared up to 120 days of age, goats of the Alpine breed consumed only 104.78 kg of feed units, 164.9 kg of dry matter, 12.31 kg of digestible protein, and by their peers the Toggenburg goats were higher by 4.04% in feed units, by 5, 23% dry matter and 3.96% digestible protein. During this period, the consumption of feed per 1 kg of weight gain for the Alpine breed was 9.7 feed units with a digestible protein content of 117.5 g, and for the kids of the Toggenburg breed, these indicators were 9.31 and 122 g, respectively.

With a technological cycle of 90 days of growth, Alpine goats consumed only 108.06 kg of feed units, 172, 48 kg of dry matter, 12.67 kg of digestible protein, and these indicators were higher than 4.09% in feed units compared to Toggenburg goats. 5.27% on dry matter basis and 3.52% on digestible protein. During this period, 10.91 feed units were consumed per 1 kg of live weight gain for the Alpine breed and 1 feed unit contained 117.2 g of digestible protein, these indicators for the Toggenburg breed were 11.67 and 118 g, respectively.

With a 60-day period of preparation for fattening, Alpine goats consumed in total 75.121 kg of feed units, 107.78 kg of dry matter, 8.81 kg of digestible protein, and these indicators are 5.63 higher than their counterparts in the Toggenburg breed by feed units, by 8.0% by dry matter and 4.87% ha digestible protein. During this period, 7.58 feed units were consumed per 1 kg of live weight gain for the Alpine breed and 1 feed unit contained 117.3 g of digestible protein, these indicators for the Toggenburg breed were 7.93 and 118.2 g, respectively.

The purpose of fattening is to demonstrate high results of the genetic potency of meat products of fattening animals, and in order to achieve these high results - a daily increase in fattening, easily digestible and readily available feed is constantly used in rations.

With a 75-day period of fattening, Alpine goats consumed 109.70 kg of feed units, 151.01 kg of dry matter, 13.18 kg of digestible protein, and these indicators are 3.47% higher than their counterparts of the Toggenburg breed in feed units, by 5.15% on dry matter and 2.94% ha of digestible protein. During this period, 7.67 feed units were consumed per 1 kg of weight gain in Alpine goats and 1 feed unit contained 120 g of digestible protein, and the indicators for the Toggenburg breed were 8.74 and 120.8 g, respectively.

2- Table

Feed consumption for the Alpine goat breed by periods of experience, kg

Stern	Experience periods, days					Total 435
	Lactic	growth	development	Feeding preparations	During the feeding period	
	Up to 90 days	Up to 120 days	Up to 90 days	Up to 60 days	Up to 75 days	
Goat milk	81	-	-	-	-	81
whole milk substitute	117	-	-	-	-	117
Hydroponic feed	14,5	-	-	-	-	14,5
Hay herbal	11	50	48	36	34	179
Straw		10	11	8	7	36
Silage from: alfalfa	14	135	153	56	100	458
triticale		57	64	23	41	185
Bran: oat		6,6	6	8,2	12,4	33,2
wheat	5,7	6,6	6	8,2	12,4	38,9
Special feed Biologically add combicorn	11	16,5	15	20,5	31	94
Cotton meal		3,5	3	4,1	6,2	16,8
Monocalcium phosphate, g	135	840	630	420	525	2550
Premix, g	150	240	180	180	225	975

Feed consumption for the Toggenburg goat breed by periods of experience, kg

Stern	Experience periods, days					Total 435
	Lactic	growth	development	Feeding preparations	During the feeding period	
	Up to 90 days	Up to 120 days	Up to 90 days	Up to 60 days	Up to 75 days	

Goat milk	81	-	-	-	-	81
whole milk substitute	117	-	-	-	-	117
Hydroponic feed	14,5	-	-	-	-	14,5
Hay herbal	11	46	45	32	31	165
Straw		8	8,5	8	5	29,5
Silage from: alfalfa	14	130	147	51	95	437
triticale		54	60	20	38	172
Bran: oat		6,6	6	8,2	12,4	33,2
wheat	5,7	6,6	6	8,2	12,4	38,9
Special feed Biologically add combigcorn	11	16,5	15	20,5	31	94
Cotton meal		3,5	3	4,1	6,2	16,8
Monocalcium phosphate, g	135	840	630	420	525	2550
Premix, g	150	240	180	180	225	975

Throughout the entire experiment lasting 435 days, Alpine goats compared to Toggenburg goats used more feed by 4.20% fodder units of feed unit, 5.72% of dry matter of feed and 3.60% of digestible protein. At the same time, per 1 kg of live weight gain, Alpine goats consumed only 7.50 kg of feed units and 127.7 g of digestible protein during the experiment, and goats of the Toggenburg breed, respectively, 7.87 feed units and 123 g of digestible protein. The difference between the breeds in terms of consumption of feed units was 4.9%, in terms of digestible protein 3.14%, with the same indicators of other criteria.

Output:

Goats of the Alpine and Toggenburg breeds adapt well to the conditions of the hot climate of Uzbekistan without losing their genetic qualities of products and can be recommended for breeding in order to diversify and supplement the diet of the population with dietary goat products.

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